

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

The Utility Of Jayanti Veda Plant Extract Containing Herbal Gel For Treatment Of Acute Veginitis

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08 Aug 2024

Accepted: 10 Aug 2024

Published: 11 Aug 2024

Keywords:

Jayanti Veda, Antibacterial, Antifungal, Veginitis, Ethanolic Extract, Herbal Gel.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13293183

ABSTRACT

This work aims to explore the preparation and assessment of herbal gel utilizing the entire Jayanti Veda plant. The wide range of applications for plant-derived chemicals and herbal medicines has garnered significant attention recently. Medicinal plants are the main source of bioactive compounds utilized in both conventional and modern medicine. Herbal medicine has gained popularity recently, and people are using it even in places where access to contemporary medical care is available. The present research aims to generate and evaluate the Jayanti Veda extract formulations in gel. Formulations were made using the ethanolic extracts. Physicochemical and morphological parameters were investigated prior to extraction. Physicochemical characteristics such as spreadability, extrudability, washability, solubility, pH, loss on drying, homogeneity, viscosity, and physical appearance were assessed when the formulations were finished, and the results were found to be good. It was also determined that the formulations were stable at different temperatures, as evidenced by the fact that the diffusion, irritancy, and spreadability studies did not vary. In light of this, it might be possible to employ Jayanti Veda therapeutic qualities in a straightforward and efficient manner using gel-like formulations. Given that the second batch of the formulation used in this investigation yielded the expected results, vaginitis may be treated with the gel formulation's antibacterial and antifungal qualities.

INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of time, medicinal plants have been a key source of cures for illnesses affecting humans. It makes sense that one-fourth of the world's population i.e. 1.42 billion people, are dependent on traditional medicines for the

treatment of various ailments [1,2]. The Indian flora offers a variety of plants having medicinal properties. These plants can be exploited to find out effective alternative to synthetic drugs [3]. Traditional medicines has importance in India since hundreds of years and it has potential action

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

on various diseases and disorders therefore it is an impactful way of treatment. As we all know, traditional medicine has many benefits, but it also has certain disadvantages, such as a paucity of research, a small body of literature, and low patient compliance. 77% of Indian families utilize ayurvedic herbal products, according to reports from certain print media outlets. [4, 5] A Jayanti Veda is a common pest and weed plant which belongs to the family *Asteraceae* and is native to America. The plant is mostly scattered in tropical Africa, Asia, and Australia and is also found all over India.[6,7] It is usually named as "coat button." Numerous pharmacological investigations on the Jayanti Veda have demonstrated that the entire plant possesses the ability to treat a wide range of conditions, including diarrhea, bronchial catarrh, hair loss, and the inhibition of bleeding from wounds. [8,9] Along with that it also showed anti-inflammatory, antihyperglycemic, wound healing, antimicrobial, antifungal and treatment of vaginitis. [10] A major cause of abnormal vaginal discharge is bacterial vaginosis (BV). It is characterized by an overabundance of mostly anaerobic organisms (*Prevotella* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp., *Peptostreptococci*, and *Gardnerella vaginalis*) in the vagina, which replaces lactobacilli and raises the pH of the vagina.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Collection Of Plant Material

Fresh whole plant of Jayanti Veda were collected from road side and authenticated by botanical department in Vikram University, Ujjain. The whole plant was washed under running tap water. Then the whole plant was shade dried for about 2-3 weeks. The dry whole plant was homogenized to fine powder or coarse powder and stored it [11].

Morphological Studies

Fig. No. 1: Plant of Jyanti Veda

- A perennial herb with a creeping stem that may grow to be 8–30 inches (20–75 cm) long is called jayanti veda.
- With wedge-shaped bases, coarsely serrated margins, and pointy apexes, the leaves of the Jayanti Veda plant are usually opposite, pinnate, rectangular to ovate, and 1-2 inches (2.55 cm) long.
- The flowers of Jayanti Veda include golden disk blossoms with white rays. They're regarding zero. 40.6 inches (1-1.5 cm) wide, and remained a 4-12 inches (10-30 cm) long stalk. Flowering happens in spring.
- Fruits make up one section. achene that range in color from dark brown to black, are rectangular, 0.08 inches (2 mm) length, and have a head of calyx bristles that may be adjusted from zero.12-0.24-inches-long (3-6 mm).
- Jayanti Veda is listed as a Federal pernicious Weed.
- It also favors sandy soils in other tropical regions. Roadsides, farms, waste ground, and fallow land are all invaded by it. Although it is indigenous to South America and Mexico, it has spread throughout the world as an invasive weed. [12].

Preparation Of Plant Extract

The entire plant of Jayanti Veda was gathered and then dried in the shade. Plant materials were coarsely pulverized and stored in tightly sealed containers after drying. In a Soxhlet system, 100g

of powdered plant leaves was extracted using ethanol at 45–55°C. The extracted materials were collected, condensed using a rotary evaporator, and stored in a vacuum dryer until needed. [13].

Phytochemical Screening Of Extract

Standard chemical tests were used for the qualitative screening of phytochemical ingredients of ethanolic extract. The presence of chemicals including Alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Fixed oils and fats, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenolic compounds, Proteins, Steroids, Tannins, Terpenes and Terpenoids were tested according to standard tests and confirmed [14]

Formulation Of Placebo Gel

First, prepare the gel formulation by dispersing carbopol 940 in distilled water (including methyl and propyl paraben) and glycerine for an overnight period. Consider the Jayanti Veda extract dissolved in propylene glycol and applied to a polymer dispersion. After that, the remaining water was added, then triethanolamine was added to bring the pH down to 7 while stirring constantly for ten minutes. [15]. On the basis of evaluation parameters such as appearance, viscosity, pH, spreadability, the placebo gel formulation of the control batch was selected (Table 1).

Table- 1: Formulation of Placebo Gel

S. No	Ingredients	Quantity	Quantity
1	Carbopol 940	1.0gm	-
2	Propylene Glycol	10.0ml	10.0ml
3	HPMC	-	1.0gm
4	Methyl Paraben	0.2ml	0.2ml
5	Propylparaben	0.1ml	0.1ml
6	Glycerine	1.0ml	1.0ml
7	Triethanolamine	Q.S.	Q.S.
8	Water	100ml	100ml

Table-2: Formulation of Gel

S.No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
1.	Extract	0.20gm	0.40gm	0.20gm	0.40gm
2.	Carbopol 940	1.0gm	1.0gm	-	-
3.	Propylene Glycol	10.0ml	10.0ml	10.0ml	10.0ml
4.	HPMC	-	-	1.0gm	1.0gm
5.	Methyl Paraben	0.2ml	0.2ml	0.2ml	0.2ml
6.	Propylparaben	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml
7.	Glycerine	1.0ml	1.0ml	1.0ml	1.0ml
8.	Triethanolamine	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.
9.	Water	100ml	100ml	100ml	100ml

Formulation Of Gel

- 20 ml of water were added to the required amount of carbopol, and it was homogenized for 15 minutes at a speed of 300 to 500 revolutions per minute.
- Once a sticky consistency is reached, add an additional 10ml of water along with triethanolamine. Once more, the stirring speed exceeded 500 RPM.
- A gel base was created after an additional 20 minutes, at which point Jayanti Veda extract was added. It was then agitated for a further 10 minutes at a higher speed. Propylene glycol, propyl paraben, and methyl paraben were then added in symmetrical proportions to create a homogenous gel. For the formulation to properly blend, add glycerin and stir for ten minutes.

4. After adding a small amount of water at a time, the entire mixture was agitated for a further forty-five minutes. [16].

Evaluation Parameters

Physicochemical Parameters

Physicochemical parameter includes moisture content, total ash, acid insoluble ash, water-soluble ash, water-soluble extractive and alcohol soluble extractive. [23,24]

Organoleptic Examination

The physical characteristics of the created formulations, including their color, texture, phase separation, and homogeneity, were examined visually. Testing for homogeneity and texture involved pressing a tiny amount of the prepared product between the thumb and index finger. The texture and homogeneity of the formulation were assessed using the presence of coarse particles and the formulation's consistency. [17]

Determination Of Viscosity

The viscosity of prepared formulations was determined using Brookfield Viscometer using Spindle S-04 at 20 RPM.

Extrudability

The formulae were put inside a tube container that could collapse. The weight of the formulations needed to extrude a 0.5-cm ointment ribbon in 10 seconds was used to measure the extrudability.

Diffusion Study

Making an agar nutrient medium allowed for the diffusion analysis of the formulations. Formulations were inserted into a whole board that was positioned in the center of the medium. It was recorded how long it took for formulations to spread. (60 minutes later). [22]

LOD

By putting the formulations on a petri dish in an oil bath and drying them at 105°C, LOD was ascertained. [22]

Solubility

Miscible with alcohol, ether, and chloroform; soluble in boiling water.

Wash Ability

After applying formulations to the skin, the ease of water washing was examined. Formulations for the non-irritancy test were produced, applied to human skin, and the results were monitored. [22]

Centrifugation Test

A 10 g portion of formulation was placed in a centrifuge tube (1 cm diameter) and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 5, 15, 30, and 60 min. Then the phase separation and solid sedimentation of the formulations were inspected [17].

Stability Test

The stability was checked by keeping formulations in Environmental stability chamber at 25° – 27 °C for 14 days. The formulations were inspected for creaming or coalescence [17, 18]

Determination Of Ph

A suspension of formulation in 1% potassium nitrate solution was prepared and its pH was determined using Digital pH meter. A magnetic stirrer was used to produce homogeneity [17, 18].

Spread Ability

Excess sample was placed between two slides and pressed to a consistent thickness using a fixed weight for a fixed amount of time to measure the spreadability. Spreadability is a measure of how long it took to separate the two slides. Better spreadability is achieved with a shorter gap period between two slides. The following formula was used to calculate spreadability.

$$S=M \times L / T$$

Where, S= Spreadability M= Weight tide to the upper slide L= Length of glass slide T= Time taken to separate the slides

Test Organism

Standard fungal strain of *Candida albicans* (grown cultures) [19] .

Antifungal Assays

1. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (Mic)

The MIC value of Jayanti Veda extract was determined using agar dilution assay. Two-fold serial dilutions of leaf extract in dimethyl

sulfoxide having a final concentration of extract ranging from 0.17% (w/v) to 14% (w/v). Control plates, containing no extract, were run simultaneously. The agar plates mixed with the dilutions of extract and the control plate were inoculated by standard inoculum (having optical density of 0.08 - 01 at 625 nm wavelength) of five-day (*C. albicans*) grown cultures. The plates were incubated at 25 °C for seven days. After incubation, the end-points for the extract were determined by placing plates on a dark background and observing the lowest concentration that inhibits visible growth, which is recorded as the MIC [19].

2. Antifungal Activity Of Topical Formulation

Antifungal activity of topical agents was performed using the method adopted in our laboratory. 30 ml of Sabouraud dextrose agar (for fungi) was added to three sterile Petri dishes and allowed to solidify. After solidification, three holes with 10 mm diameter was made by cutting out plug of agar at equal distance in each plate using sterile cork-borer. The plates were inoculated by standard inoculum of *C. albicans* using cotton swab. About 1 ml of designated topical formulations were added to two wells followed by adding 1 ml of designated commercial topical formulation in third well of each plate. The plate was inverted, left to rest at room temperature for an hour, and then incubated at 25 °C for seven days after solidifying for two to three minutes. Following incubation, measurements were made of the inhibition zones' diameters. [18, 20, ,21].

Drug Content

After correctly weighing one gram of gel, it was transferred to a 100 milliliter volumetric flask and around 70 milliliters of distilled water were added. After mixing, volume was made up to 100ml with

distilled water. The content was filtered through suitable filter paper. An aliquot of 1ml was pipette out from filtrate. The extract was estimated spectrophotometrically by using Shimadzu UV-VIS Spectrophotometer- 1700 at 281 nm [25]

In Vitro Diffusion Study

In order to investigate the dissolution release pattern of the gel via the cellophane membrane, diffusion investigations of the produced gel formulations were conducted in Franz Diffusion Cell. Gel sample (1gm) was taken on cellophane membrane and the diffusion studies were carried out at 37± 1oC using distilled water as dissolution medium. Five milliliters of each sample was withdrawn periodically at an interval of 1 hour for 8 hours and each sample was replaced with equal volume of dissolution medium. The samples were analyzed for drug content by using distilled water as blank [2]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The goal of the current study was to prepare and assess the formulations. The Soxhlet technique was used to create the herbal extracts for this. Plant physicochemical parameters and initial phytochemical screening were carried out. The assessment parameters were examined, and the findings for spreadability, extrudability, washability, solubility, pH, loss on drying, homogeneity, viscosity, and physical appearance are satisfactory. Additionally, the formulations were subjected to a stability investigation for 14 days at 25–27 °C in temperature settings. Furthermore, no alterations were seen in the diffusion study or spreading ability.

1. Physicochemical Parameter

The values for physicochemical parameter are tabulated in

Table-3: Physicochemical constant of plant: Sample identity

S.no.	Physicochemical constant	% Value
1.	% LOD	13
2.	% Total Ash	11.88
3.	Acid insoluble ash %	3.05

4.	Water soluble ash %	2.14
5.	Water soluble Extractive value%	28.16
6.	Alcohol soluble Extractive value%	07.17

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening Of Extract

Table-4: Phytoconstituents present in ethanolic extract of Jayanti Veda

S.no.	Phytoconstituents	Plant Extract
1.	Alkaloids	+
2.	Glycosides	-
3.	Steroids	+
4.	carbohydrates	+
5.	Flavonoids	+
6.	Phenolic Compounds	+
7.	Terpenes and Terpenoids	+
8.	Fixed Oils and Fats	+
9.	Tannins	+
10.	Proteins	+

Evaluation Of Gel Formulation

Table-5: Evaluation of gel formulation

S.no.	Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4
1.	Physical Appearance	Transparent	Transparent	Transparent	Transparent
2.	Color	Pale Green	Pale Green	Pale Green	Pale Green
3.	Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
4.	Phase Separation	Clear	Clear	Clear	Clear
5.	Homogeneity	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous
6.	Viscosity (Poise)	0.3842	0.3871	0.3979	0.3715
7.	pH	7.8	7.9	7.4	7.6
8.	Extrudability (%)	99.45	94.56	99.95	97.85
9.	LOD (%)	30	25	28	32
10.	Wash ability	Adequate	Adequate	Adequate	Adequate
11.	Solubility	Soluble in boiling water, miscible with alcohol, ether, chloroform	Soluble in boiling water, miscible with alcohol, ether, chloroform	Soluble in boiling water, miscible with alcohol, ether, chloroform	Soluble in boiling water, miscible with alcohol, ether, chloroform
12.	Centrifugation Test	Distortion	Distortion	Distortion	Distortion
13.	Stability Test	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable
14.	Spread ability (gcm/sec)	74.7	76.12	75.41	60.21

Test Organism

Table-6: Zone of inhibition in Diameter (mm)

Fungal Yeast	Zone of inhibition in Diameter (mm)				
	Standard	F1	F2	F3	F4
Candida albicans	28	20	25	24	23

Drug Content:

Drug content of formulation F1-F4 showed in table 7. The maximum drug content was found in formulation F2.

Table-7: Drug content of formulation

S. No	Formulation	Drug Content (%)
1	F1	89.77
2	F2	94.44
3	F3	92.88
4	F4	91.22

In Vitro Diffusion Study

In vitro diffusion study was carried out in diffusion cell for 8 hours, showed F2 formulation with

maximum drug release as compared to other gel formulations showed in table 8.

Table-8: In vitro diffusion study

Time (hr)	% Drug Release			
	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
1	26.35	32.30	20.90	25.31
2	28.83	37.05	30.05	29.56
3	32.42	45.04	36.30	37.26
4	38.16	57.53	45.40	49.63
5	44.34	62.16	51.60	54.17
6	59.26	70.76	69.50	63.98
7	79.94	88.45	77.00	69.74
8	87.46	94.61	86.30	78.50

Fig. No. 2: Viscosity and pH of herbal gel containing Jayanti Veda ethanolic extract

Fig. No. 3: Extrudability, spreadability and LOD of herbal gel containing Jayanti Veda ethanolic extract

Fig. No. 4: Antimicrobial Activity of herbal gel containing Jayanti Veda ethanolic extract

Fig. No. 5: Drug content of herbal gel containing Jayanti Veda ethanolic extract

Fig. No. 6: Drug Release of herbal gel containing Jayanti Veda ethanolic extract

CONCLUSION

Given that the second batch of the current study's formulation produced desired results, the gel formulation's antibacterial and antifungal properties may be utilized to treat vaginitis. The phytochemicals are found in many compounds and are active, making them bioactive compounds with a variety of medicinal uses. Given their perceived effectiveness and lower side effect profile compared to synthetic medicines, natural remedies are more widely accepted. Global demand for herbal formulations is rising. The attempt to create the herbal gel formulation with Jayanti Veda ethanolic extract is excellent.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all those who have contributed to the successful completion of this research. I would also like to acknowledge Indore Institute of Pharmacy, Indore for providing the necessary resources and facilities that made this research possible. Thank you all for your contributions and support.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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HOW TO CITE: Nisha Retrekar*, Deepika Bhawsar, Gaurav Agrawal, Gaurav Sarsodia, The Utility Of Jayanti Veda Plant Extract Containing Herbal Gel For Treatment Of Acute Veginitis, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2024, Vol 2, Issue 8, 2957-2967. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13293183>